

Kinetics of Oxidation of Acetaldehyde by Chloramine-T in Acid Medium

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The kinetics of oxidation of acetaldehyde by Chloramine-T in HCl, HClO₄ and H₂SO₄ media shows a first order dependence each on oxidant, substrate and [H⁺] ion concentrations, but the rate law reduces to Rate = k [CAT] at higher aldehyde and hydrogen ion concentrations. A mechanism in terms of a slow interaction between N-chlorotoluenesulphonamide and the aldehyde molecule is proposed.

SODIUM N-chloro-4-methyl-benzene-sulphonamide or Chloramine-T (CAT) behaves as an oxidizing agent in both acidic and alkaline media and some of these chloraminometric reactions have been kinetically investigated¹. Quantitative oxidation of aldehydes and kinetic studies of oxidation of some aliphatic aldehydes by alkaline CAT have been made, but reports on oxidation of aldehydes by CAT in acid medium are lacking. The present work has shown some interesting observations in the oxidation of acetaldehyde by CAT in acid medium at 40°.

Experimental

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified by the method of Morris and Co-workers². Aqueous solutions of acetaldehyde (AnalaR, B.D.H.) were prepared and standardized. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

The kinetic studies were carried out at an ionic strength of 0.5M (NaClO₄) at 40° in a thermostat under pseudo first order conditions. The rate of reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted CAT iodometrically. The rate constants calculated graphically were reproducible to ±3%. Stoichiometric determination shows that one mole of aldehyde consumes one mole of CAT confirming oxidation to acetic acid. Toluenesulphonamide formed was detected by paper chromatography³.

Results and Discussion

At constant acid concentration (HCl, HClO₄ = 0.1M and H₂SO₄ = 0.05M) and in presence of excess aldehyde, plots of log [CAT] vs time are linear indicating first order dependence of the rate on the concentration of oxidant. The pseudo first order rate constants k' are given in Table 1. Values of k' increases with substrate concentration at low values (0.2M). The values of k'/[substrate] are found to be constant. However, values of k' becomes constant beyond 0.2 M, the reaction rate

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

$\mu = 0.5M$		Temp. = 40 ± 0.1°		
10 ³ [CAT]M	10[CH ₃ CHO]M	HCl	HClO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄
		10 ⁴ k' sec ⁻¹		
2.0	1.00	2.60	2.35	2.42
3.0	1.00	2.65	2.39	2.42
4.0	1.00	2.66	2.41	2.42
5.0	1.00	2.65	2.40	2.44
6.0	1.00	2.66	2.40	2.42
4.0	0.50	—	1.11	—
4.0	0.70	—	1.86	—
4.0	1.25	—	2.88	—
4.0	1.50	4.12	3.80	3.65
4.0	2.00	5.78	3.12	4.75
4.0	2.50	7.07	3.00	6.10
4.0	3.00	8.19	2.99	7.26
4.0	3.50	10.00	2.98	7.95
4.0	4.00	11.50	—	7.97
4.0	4.50	—	—	7.97
4.0	5.00	14.20	—	7.98
4.0	6.00	15.90	—	7.98
4.0	7.00	15.90	—	—
4.0	8.00	16.00	—	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE OF REACTION

[CAT] ₀ = 0.004M ; [CH ₃ CHO] = 0.1M $\mu = 0.5M$; Temp. = 40 ± 0.1°						
10 ³ [H ⁺] M	HCl		HClO ₄		H ₂ SO ₄	
	10 ⁴ k'	10 ³ k'/[H ⁺]	10 ⁴ k'	10 ³ k'/[H ⁺]	10 ⁴ k'	10 ³ k'/[H ⁺]
2.0	—	—	0.45	2.25	—	—
3.0	1.60	5.33	—	—	—	—
4.0	2.09	5.22	—	—	—	—
5.0	2.66	5.32	1.10	2.20	2.48	4.86
6.0	3.21	5.35	—	—	2.92	4.86
7.0	3.68	5.25	—	—	3.39	4.75
8.0	4.23	5.29	1.87	2.33	3.90	4.88
9.0	—	—	—	—	4.32	4.80
10.0	4.36	4.36	2.45	2.45	4.84	4.84
12.5	—	—	2.69	2.15	—	—
15.0	—	—	2.55	—	4.85	—
20.0	4.36	—	2.71	—	4.85	—
25.0	—	—	2.57	—	4.84	—
30.0	4.37	—	2.65	—	4.85	—
35.0	—	—	2.59	—	—	—
40.0	4.37	—	—	—	—	—

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increases with $[H^+]$ and a first order dependence of rate on H^+ is seen below $0.1M$. The rate becomes constant beyond $0.1M$ indicating zero order dependence in $[H^+]$ (Table 2). Addition of chloride ion in the form of $NaCl$ (0.05 to $0.3M$) or the reaction product *p*-toluenesulphonamide (0.005 to $0.02M$) has no effect on the rate. The rate was not affected when the ionic strength of the medium was varied from 0.4 to $1.0M$. However, addition of methanol decreases the rate (Table 3). The reaction

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF METHANOL ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

$[CAT]=0.004M$; $[OH_2COOH]=0.1M$; $[H^+]=0.1M$ for $HClO_4$,
 $[H^+]=0.05M$ for H_2SO_4 ,
 and HCl

%MeOH	$10^4 k'_{\text{sec}^{-1}}$		
	HCl	$HClO_4$	H_2SO_4
10	1.60	1.57	1.45
20	1.25	1.11	1.14
30	1.04	0.99	0.95
40	0.77	0.69	0.70
50	0.59	0.49	0.54

was studied at different temperatures (40 to 55°) and the Arrhenius parameters have been evaluated. They are :

Medium	E_a , $KJ/mole$	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$, Jk^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger , $KJ/mole$	ΔG^\ddagger , $KJ/mole$
HCl	52.67	153.9	50.00	90.9
$HClO_4$	61.54	126.5	58.90	67.1
H_2SO_4	55.10	147.2	52.40	100.0

The oxidation of aldehydes in general has been found to be either acid or base catalyzed. Drummond and Waters⁴ have found that the rate of oxidation of aldehydes by manganic pyrophosphate follows zero order dependence in oxidant, as also the oxidation of several carbonyl compounds by alkaline ferricyanide. Enolization of aldehydes may be rate determining depending on the subsequent reaction between enol-anion and the oxidant.

Chloramine-T in acid solution contains the anion ($RNCl^-$), *N*-chloro-*p*-toluene-sulphonamide ($RNHCl$), dichloramine-T ($RNCl_2$) and $HOCl$. The first order dependence of rate on $[CAT]$ and negligible effect of *p*-toluenesulphonamide on the reaction indicate that $RNCl_2$ and $HOCl$ are not the active species in the present set of experiments. Ionic strength of the medium has no effect on the rate indicating that neutral species are involved in the rate determining step. In view of this, the following scheme may be proposed for the reaction to account for the observed kinetics.

If $[CAT]_T$ is the total concentration of CAT

$[CAT]_T = [RNCl^-] + [RNHCl] + [X]$, from which the value of $[X]$ can be shown to be

$$[X] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [CAT]_T [CH_3CHO] [H^+]}{1 + K_1 [H^+] \{1 + K_2 [CH_3CHO]\}} \quad \dots (1)$$

As $\text{Rate} = k_s [X]$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_s K_1 K_2 [CAT]_T [CH_3CHO] [H^+]}{1 + K_1 [H^+] \{1 + K_2 [CH_3CHO]\}} \quad \dots (2)$$

At low $[H^+]$ and $[CH_3CHO]$, neglecting $K_1 [H^+]$ and $K_1 K_2 [H^+] [CH_3CHO]$, compared to unity, equation (2) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_s K_1 K_2 [CAT]_T [CH_3CHO] [H^+] \quad \dots (3)$$

At higher concentrations the inequality

$K_1 K_2 [CH_3CHO] [H^+] > \{1 + K_1 [H^+]\}$ holds good and the rate law (2) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_s [CAT]_T \quad \dots (4)$$

The rate laws (3) and (4) are in agreement with experimental results. The negative methanol-effect shows that the rate determining step involves two dipolar species or a negative ion and a dipole⁵.

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